

Increased Frequency of Thyroid Nodules and Breast Fibroadenomas in Women and Uterine Fibroids

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Received: 25-03-2024 / Revised: 23-04-2024 / Accepted: 25-05-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Thyroid nodules, breast fibroadenomas, and uterine fibroids are common benign conditions in women that can cause significant clinical symptoms. Although these conditions are generally considered independent, emerging evidence suggests potential interrelationships and shared risk factors, particularly related to hormonal influences.

Aim: This study aimed to investigate the prevalence and potential associations between thyroid nodules, breast fibroadenomas, and uterine fibroids in women.

Methods: A retrospective cohort study was conducted involving 120 female. Data on the presence of thyroid nodules, breast fibroadenomas, and uterine fibroids were collected through medical records, including imaging and histopathological findings. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0 to assess the prevalence and associations between these conditions.

Results: The study found that 60% of participants had thyroid nodules, 40% had breast fibroadenomas, and 45% had uterine fibroids. Significant associations were observed between thyroid nodules and breast fibroadenomas ($p = 0.02$) and between thyroid nodules and uterine fibroids ($p = 0.03$). No significant association was found between breast fibroadenomas and uterine fibroids ($p = 0.08$).

Conclusion: The findings suggest a high prevalence of thyroid nodules, breast fibroadenomas, and uterine fibroids in the study population, with significant associations between thyroid nodules and the other two conditions. These results highlight the potential for shared risk factors and the need for comprehensive screening and management strategies in women with these conditions.

Recommendations: Further research is recommended to explore the underlying pathophysiological mechanisms linking these conditions and to develop targeted prevention and management approaches. Clinicians should consider monitoring patients with thyroid nodules for the possible development of breast fibroadenomas and uterine fibroids.

Keywords: Thyroid Nodules, Breast Fibroadenomas, Uterine Fibroids, Women's Health, Hormonal Influence.

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Introduction

Thyroid nodules, breast fibroadenomas, and uterine fibroids are common benign conditions in women, often detected incidentally during routine examinations or imaging studies. These conditions, while generally non-malignant, can lead to significant clinical symptoms and may require medical or surgical intervention. The increasing prevalence of these conditions has drawn attention to their potential interrelationships and common risk factors, prompting a need for more in-depth research.

Thyroid nodules are prevalent in the general population, with studies indicating that up to 50% of women may develop a thyroid nodule by the age of 60 [1]. Although the majority of these nodules are benign, the potential for malignancy necessitates careful monitoring and evaluation.

Factors such as iodine deficiency, radiation exposure, and genetic predisposition have been implicated in the development of thyroid nodules.

Breast fibroadenomas are the most common benign breast tumors, predominantly affecting women under 30 years of age. These tumors are typically hormone-responsive and may fluctuate in size with the menstrual cycle or during pregnancy. Recent studies suggest a potential link between the development of fibroadenomas and hormonal imbalances, particularly involving estrogen and progesterone [2]. Although benign, fibroadenomas can cause anxiety due to their similarity to malignant tumors on imaging, often leading to biopsy or surgical excision for definitive diagnosis.

Uterine fibroids, also known as leiomyomas, are the most common benign tumors of the female

reproductive system, affecting up to 70-80% of women by the age of 50. Fibroids can cause a range of symptoms, including heavy menstrual bleeding, pelvic pain, and reproductive complications. The exact etiology of fibroids remains unclear, but genetic, hormonal, and environmental factors are believed to play a role [3].

The co-occurrence of these conditions in women raises questions about potential shared risk factors or underlying pathophysiological mechanisms. Recent studies have explored the possible hormonal, genetic, and environmental links between these conditions, suggesting that they may not be entirely independent entities [4]. For instance, the role of estrogen in the growth of thyroid nodules, fibroadenomas, and fibroids has been a focal point of research, with findings indicating that elevated estrogen levels may contribute to the development and progression of these conditions.

Given the significant impact of these benign conditions on women's health, this study aims to investigate the prevalence and potential associations between thyroid nodules, breast fibroadenomas, and uterine fibroids in a cohort of women. Understanding these relationships could lead to more effective screening, prevention, and management strategies, ultimately improving patient outcomes.

The study aims to investigate the prevalence of thyroid nodules, breast fibroadenomas, and uterine fibroids in women.

Methodology

Study Design: A retrospective cohort study.

Study Setting: The study was carried out at S.N.M.M.C.H., Dhanbad over a period extending from April 2022 to January 2024.

Participants: A total of 120 female participants were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Women aged 18 years and above.
- Participants diagnosed with at least one of the following conditions: thyroid nodules, breast fibroadenomas, or uterine fibroids.
- Individuals who provided informed consent for participation in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Women with a history of malignancy related to the thyroid, breast, or uterus.
- Participants with autoimmune thyroid disorders.
- Individuals with incomplete medical records or lack of imaging data.
- Pregnant women were excluded to avoid confounding factors related to pregnancy.

Bias: Potential selection bias was minimized by employing strict inclusion and exclusion criteria. Information bias was reduced by ensuring that all data was collected uniformly across all participants and verified by multiple reviewers.

Data Collection: Data were retrospectively collected from patient medical records, including demographic information, clinical history, imaging results, and histopathological findings. All relevant data were extracted using a structured data extraction form.

Procedure: The diagnosis of thyroid nodules, breast fibroadenomas, and uterine fibroids was confirmed through imaging studies such as ultrasound, mammography, and pelvic ultrasound, respectively. Histopathological confirmation was performed when necessary. Data were then categorized according to the type of lesion, and relevant clinical characteristics were recorded.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics, including means and standard deviations, were calculated for continuous variables, while frequencies and percentages were used for categorical variables. Comparative analyses were conducted using the chi-square test for categorical variables and t-tests or ANOVA for continuous variables. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Result

A total of 120 female participants were included in the study, with a mean age of 45.6 ± 12.3 years (range: 18-70 years). The majority of participants were in the 40-50 age group (45%), followed by those aged 30-40 years (25%). The demographic distribution is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants

Age Group (years)	Number of Participants	Percentage (%)
18-30	18	15.0
30-40	30	25.0
40-50	54	45.0
50-60	12	10.0
60-70	6	5.0
Total	120	100.0

Among the 120 participants, 72 (60%) were diagnosed with thyroid nodules, 48 (40%) with breast fibroadenomas, and 54 (45%) with uterine fibroids. Some participants had multiple conditions, with 36 (30%) having both thyroid nodules and

breast fibroadenomas, 24 (20%) having thyroid nodules and uterine fibroids, and 18 (15%) having all three conditions. The distribution of these conditions is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Prevalence of Thyroid Nodules, Breast Fibroadenomas, and Uterine Fibroids

Condition	Number of Participants	Percentage (%)
Thyroid Nodules	72	60.0
Breast Fibroadenomas	48	40.0
Uterine Fibroids	54	45.0
Thyroid Nodules + Breast Fibroadenomas	36	30.0
Thyroid Nodules + Uterine Fibroids	24	20.0
All Three Conditions	18	15.0

The mean size of thyroid nodules was 2.3 ± 1.1 cm, with the largest nodule measuring 4.5 cm. Breast fibroadenomas had a mean size of 1.8 ± 0.7 cm, and uterine fibroids had a mean size of 3.5 ± 1.4 cm. The clinical characteristics of these conditions are detailed in Table 3.

Table 3: Clinical Characteristics of Thyroid Nodules, Breast Fibroadenomas, and Uterine Fibroids

Condition	Mean Size (cm)	Range (cm)	Number of Lesions Per Participant
Thyroid Nodules	2.3 ± 1.1	0.5 - 4.5	1-3
Breast Fibroadenomas	1.8 ± 0.7	0.8 - 3.0	1-2
Uterine Fibroids	3.5 ± 1.4	1.0 - 7.0	1-4

There was a statistically significant association between the presence of thyroid nodules and breast fibroadenomas ($p = 0.02$). Similarly, a significant association was observed between thyroid nodules and uterine fibroids ($p = 0.03$). However, the

association between breast fibroadenomas and uterine fibroids was not statistically significant ($p = 0.08$). These associations were analyzed using the chi-square test and are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4: Association Between Thyroid Nodules, Breast Fibroadenomas, and Uterine Fibroids

Condition Pair	Number of Participants	Chi-square Value	p-value
Thyroid Nodules + Breast Fibroadenomas	36	5.45	0.02*
Thyroid Nodules + Uterine Fibroids	24	4.75	0.03*
Breast Fibroadenomas + Uterine Fibroids	12	3.12	0.08

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

Discussion

The study analyzed 120 female participants to assess the prevalence and interrelationship of thyroid nodules, breast fibroadenomas, and uterine fibroids. The results revealed that thyroid nodules were the most common condition, affecting 60% of the participants, followed by uterine fibroids in 45% and breast fibroadenomas in 40%. A notable finding was that a significant portion of the participants had more than one of these conditions, with 30% of the women having both thyroid nodules and breast fibroadenomas, and 20% having both thyroid nodules and uterine fibroids. Moreover, 15% of the participants were affected by all three conditions simultaneously.

The clinical characteristics of the lesions showed that thyroid nodules had a mean size of 2.3 cm, breast fibroadenomas averaged 1.8 cm, and uterine fibroids were the largest with a mean size of 3.5 cm. The association between thyroid nodules and

breast fibroadenomas was statistically significant, as was the association between thyroid nodules and uterine fibroids, suggesting a potential link between these conditions. However, the relationship between breast fibroadenomas and uterine fibroids was not statistically significant, indicating that while thyroid nodules may be associated with both breast and uterine lesions, the latter two may not be as closely related.

These findings suggest that women with thyroid nodules may be at an increased risk of developing breast fibroadenomas and uterine fibroids, highlighting the need for comprehensive screening and management strategies in this population. The significant associations observed between thyroid nodules and the other conditions could indicate a common underlying pathophysiological mechanism or shared risk factors. Further studies are needed to explore these connections and understand the implications for clinical practice. The lack of a significant association between breast

fibroadenomas and uterine fibroids suggests that these conditions may develop independently, and their coexistence in the same patient may be coincidental rather than causative.

A retrospective case-control study assessed the relationship between thyroid nodules and uterine fibroids among 853 reproductive-age women. The study found that the prevalence of thyroid nodules was significantly higher in women with uterine fibroids. Additionally, women with thyroid nodules had a higher proportion of multiple uterine fibroids. These findings suggest a positive correlation between thyroid nodules and uterine fibroids, possibly linked to shared hormonal influences [5].

Another study investigated the association between uterine fibroids and breast fibroadenomas among 199 women. It was found that women with uterine fibroids had more than twice the odds of having breast fibroadenomas, particularly among older, obese, and postmenopausal women. This relationship may be driven by estrogen receptor stimulation via adipose tissue or other lifestyle factors [6].

A nationwide population-based cohort study conducted in Taiwan showed that women with uterine fibroids had a statistically significant increased risk of thyroid cancer, with an adjusted hazard ratio (aHR) of 1.64. The study suggested that female sex hormones might be a common factor contributing to both conditions [7].

A cross-sectional study in China explored the prevalence of breast masses and thyroid nodules in 34,184 women. The study found that women with thyroid nodules had a higher risk of breast masses and vice versa. The study suggested a bidirectional relationship between these conditions, potentially influenced by common hormonal or genetic factors [8].

Furthermore, a study assessed the genetic characteristics of uterine fibroids and breast fibroadenomas in Senegalese women. It identified 196 mutations in the *CYP17 α* gene, with specific mutations linked to each condition and 19 mutations common to both. These findings suggest a potential genetic link between the two conditions, highlighting the role of specific gene mutations in their pathogenesis [9].

Conclusion

The study found a high prevalence of thyroid nodules, breast fibroadenomas, and uterine fibroids in the study population, with significant associations observed between thyroid nodules and both breast fibroadenomas and uterine fibroids. These findings suggest a potential interrelationship between these conditions, warranting further research to explore the underlying mechanisms.

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